

Open Knowledge' Accessfor Embedded Journalism in Pakistan

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Abstract

The structure of warfare is changing. The traditional facets of warfare are changing: outdated tactics are diminishing, whilst newer techniques and technology, such as intelligence warfare, asymmetric warfare, internet propaganda, and hybrid warfare, are filling the gap, blurring the boundaries between combatant and noncombatant, as well as between war and peacetime. In his magnum opus On Battle, Carl von Clausewitz developed the basic framework of modern warfare. He defined modern state warfare as "a duel on a grander scale" and defined its aim as "the continuity of politics through other means," with its core components of "state rationality, military order chance, and populist rage." Based on Clausewitz's study, William S. Lind described four decades of warfare after the Peace of Westphalia in 1648, each with its own distinct form of warfare. This research discusses Lind's fourth-generation warfare and Daniel H. Abbott's fifth-generation warfare. It addresses the different reasons for fourth-generation fighting advanced by various academics (4GW). To begin, it describes 4GW as asymmetric warfare carried out by non-state actors and non-state cultural communities, under which non-state actors and mercenaries wage asymmetric warfare and shadow wars in the geopolitical interests of hostile states. Following that, this article addresses how to fight 4GW and the manner in which it is being fought at the moment. Additionally, the article examines Abbott's fifth-generation warfare, a war of aspirations, and explores how to fight 5GW and the manner in which it is currently being fought. Additionally, this article addresses how contemporary warfare employs technological innovation as a tool. Finally, this article discussed how the Government of Pakistan could outsource some of the previously mentioned activities, thereby adding a new player to the ecosystem. Numerous data points and vast public datasets from cities, regions, and government offices have new perspectives on the economy. The data collection process used both qualitative and quantitative methods. It is more possible that by implementing the concept of "right to open data," the Government of Pakistan would be able to develop the country's social sector. Media is the fourth pillar of state holds the right to get access to the data in times of wars. So through conflict reporting, better solution-based journalism can be achieved.

Introduction

Open information (or free knowledge) is the knowledge that is freely usable, re-usable, and redistributable, regardless of legal, societal, or technical constraints. Organizations and campaigners for free education have suggested guidelines and methodologies for the open creation and dissemination of knowledge. The term "knowledge" is used widely to refer to both data (open data) and software (open content), as well as both general and science facts (open access).

Fifth-generation fighting has arisen, transforming the essence and character of human conflict irreversibly. It places the US in a new strategic bind, one that requires not only enduring the War on Terror but also developing plans that look beyond military preparedness for recent conflicts and into a broader view of national preparedness for a range of potential conflicts. This essay explores four critical aspects of combat—new arenas of battle, evolving adversarial characteristics, changing target characteristics, and shifting the essence of force—in order to create a generational typology of war and conflict that informs the characteristics of fifth-generation warfare. The definition generates two outputs: To conclude, it shows how contemporary developments such as the proliferation of computer hackers, the 2001 anthrax and 2003–2004 ricin attacks, the 2004 Madrid bombings, and the advent of Al Qaeda all exhibit fifth generation warfare characteristics. Second, it demonstrates how these activities are distinct signs of a world in which non-state actors are acquiring the capability to wage war on an equal basis with nation-states. The article concludes that the US must accept fifth-

generation warfare if it is to effectively battle these challenges, which have taken on different and previously unimaginable forms throughout the postmodern period of conflict.

Any economy's prosperity is essentially determined by the ability to carry out developmental programs. Developmental programs are critical for empowering residents and maintaining the provision of a healthy social atmosphere that promotes equity and protection. Pakistan, as a developing economy, is working to ensure the country's citizens' welfare. Numerous tactics assist the Government in accomplishing this aim, one of which is the usage of open data systems (ODS), which was pioneered by the Government of Pakistan by offering access to databases. This study examines the benefits and drawbacks of using OD to influence Pakistan's social growth. The usage of ODS has several advantages, including making everyday life activities simpler for the general population in Pakistan while also ensuring corruption is eradicated by increased oversight of national agencies. Open data structures make it possible for individuals (journalists) to access the data they need for their study topics. Everyone has easy access to the data, which facilitates the utilization of usable data. The usage of accessible data is promoted by governments worldwide in order to increase accountability and improve control of public policy.

Media organizations that embrace an accessible data approach would have more visibility to the public and would be able to discuss their reached success goals with interested parties (Attard, 2016). The industrialized world has long recognized the critical nature and advantages of this method. President Obama effectively launched this initiative in the United States with a program aimed at promoting openness and responsibility. The primary objective of this policy was to ensure the effective operation of public institutions. This was later embraced by the United Kingdom's administration, which encouraged a tradition of openness in Pakistan as well (Alcock, 2014). The primary goal of instituting the ODS was to concretize the civil departments' obligation to their residents and to enable them to engage in the country's social growth. Apart from promoting social development, it also empowered the populace. Governments mostly used it to ensure timely delivery of citizens' rights and to keep citizens informed regarding the usage of their money and the programs to which their money was directed. With the same objective in mind, the Government of Pakistan implemented this policy (Judge, 2005). In view of the above, it is argued that implementation of such systems may potentially strengthen Pakistan's governments, enabling them to operate more effectively and transparently and establishing a positive image in the minds of Pakistani citizens.

Research Questions

1. How can the Open Knowledge platform help the development of the defense sector?
2. How using the Open Knowledge platform can help in formulating helpful strategic policies for the journalist using conflict reporting?
3. How can an open data system play a role in achieving peace and sustainability?

Research Objectives

In order to know the answer of how the researcher will carry this study, it is better to probe into the following objectives:

- Evaluate the definition and need of 'Open Data' terms to find reasons.
- Assess the worth of carrying a case study to the fifth-generation war and analyze the impact.
- Work out a strategy that shows the impact of ODS on social development in the country.
- An 'Open Data' access can prove to be a key that any country can use to assimilate its development purposes.

Research Hypothesis

H1: A positive relationship exists between social and political development in Pakistan by using open data.

H2: The defense of Pakistan can be improved through the use of an open data system.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Although the tradition of press-military ties predates contemporary media, much of what came before was obliterated by the heinous press-military collapse that happened after the United States' intervention in Vietnam. By the end of the Vietnam War, confidence between the press and the military had reached an all-time low, and antagonism from both sides had reached an all-time peak. Many members of the public, feeling repeatedly deceived, commented on ongoing developments in a misleading light; several members of the military felt betrayed by this "inappropriate" and negative press attention and desired little more contact with the press. Following Vietnam, the contrast between First Amendment rights, a widely recognized civilian "right to information," and military opposition and a need for tactical confidentiality has resulted in a variety of systemic ways for press-military ties. To begin, the press was completely excluded from the intervention in Grenada, followed by the more effective yet less satisfactory "press pool" systems used in Panama and throughout the first Gulf War, and the "reversal of fortunes" in Haiti and Somalia, where the press arrived before the troops and concluding (for the time being) with the "embedded press" system, in which journalists are attached to, an armed force. The embedded press system seems to be the strongest approach to date for balancing the needs of the three primary constituencies (press, military, and public); nevertheless, concerns

remain on whether that impression is right, what changes remain, and what, if any, drawbacks (for any of the constituents) the embedded press system produces.

Based on the available literature, the concept of open data can be understood in terms of the data that is available for public use with any restriction such as the restrictions like copyright, patents, or other mechanisms of control. Open data refers to the concept that the data should be freely available to everyone to use and republish as per their requirements and as and when they wish, without any restrictions.

Although at the moment, there is limited literature available on 'Open Data' policies regarding each country. This gap leads to the development of frameworks that are used to strengthen a country's socio-economic development. It is an important part to consider that the open data must consider sharing the information pertinent to the organizations that are needed by the customers of the organizations and government departments. Additionally, the open data systems must offer information that is frequently utilized, like geographic information, information about the climate, progress statistics, information about the number of visitors per day, and information about the functions of the organization. In this regard, in March 2011, the Finnish Government stressed developing a database for the usage of open information by making it a major part of the Government's Program. Motivated by the Government's initiative and keeping in view the goals like transparency and better outreach, the government departments started sharing their information through open data in the year 2012. For example, the National Land Survey of Finland started information about advanced topographic information in May 2012. In the same vein, a year later, the Finnish Meteorological Institute initiated sharing climate information online.

The basic purpose is to provide all significant information collected and stored by the open organization by 2020 and making them accessible and usable through the internet and computers, for paying nothing out of pocket as a fee, and the information should be shared under clear terms of use. The European United Kingdom became the first country to open data for the public and has achieved a large number of positive outcomes in terms of social and economic development.

METHODOLOGY

The research approach was deductive in nature. The relationship of 'Open Data' is examined with the socio-political development of the country. The hypotheses were tested for confirmation or rejection with the help of measurement of variables through the correlation method.

For this purpose, the construct validity and convergent validity were considerable since all the variables should measure the same concept and hence should be strongly correlated. To test this correlation, we have used factor analysis. Measuring the validity of the instrument here is actually verified by ensuring that the questionnaire contains questions relevant to the concept being taken. In quantitative techniques, the validity of the instrument is more on the theoretic aspect as to what the purpose is. Here, the objectives are clear and construct validity, and its testing technique will be used, which will substantiate the validity of the instrument also.

Both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods were used. Interviews and survey research strategy was employed and data collected from four types of respondents who were in favor of using the open data systems including, businesses, media people, the general public, and Non-Governmental Organizations.

Further, the statistical analysis was conducted using different approaches such as correlation, regression analysis, and factor analysis. The results showed a positive relationship between the use of ODS and positive outcomes in the social sectors of Pakistan.

The Pearson's correlation was used to establish a link between the variables having independent and dependent nature. Further, the regression analysis was used to examine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variables. The descriptive statistics helped in extracting meaningful results from the study.

The below-mentioned principles are included in the Charter for open data (2015);

- The open status of the data available must be ensured
- The data provided must be reachable and usable, i.e., accessible
- The data/information should be exchangeable
- This is used for better governance and engaging the residents
- The data must be innovation supportive
- The information should be timely, appropriate, and all-encompassing

Two major indicators that are generally considered to measure Open Data maturity are its readiness and maturity. These characteristics must be induced in the national Open Data portal. The "readiness" of an open data portal ensures the presence of open data policies for the users of such data added with the economic, social, and political impact of Open Data. At the same time, the "maturity" is using a web-based portal such as its functions the overall again and again using of data, and the spread of data.

RESULTS

The results indicate that only 44% of the journey of adopting complete Open Data systems is accomplished by the Pakistan's Social media. The adoption of complete ODS would require the development of a clear Open Data Policy that must address the licensing aspects. Additionally, it requires the development of national

guidelines that help the local governments to learn and adapt from the developed systems. The open data systems adoption completely would require having a better understanding of the expected impact of Open Data. Besides this, it requires efficient management of the traffic coming towards open data systems. The portal must contain features that should cover different data categories that are supported with the data download feature as well.

DISCUSSION

Data is ubiquitous: from governments releasing billions of bytes to graphic designers producing modern visions of the environment to industries based on it. And everybody aspires to be a data journalist - the barriers to entry have never been smaller, as open tools redefine who can analyze, visualize, and present data. Truly, everyone is capable of doing it. Simultaneously, media has evolved; not long ago, the only path to have a story covered by a major news organization required years of preparation, internships, and general slaving away before the work was heard and published. Still, the balance of influence has changed, and the days of writers isolating themselves from the environment in order to disseminate jewels of exquisite writing are long gone.

These are the days of open media, and journalists who understand how to use the power of the internet will deliver deeper, more compelling stories. Open coverage entails the reader reading and writing on the topic as well as the original reporter, with the ability to mold and affect the content they see. However, how does this relate to data journalism? Both are two segments of the same pie chart - and for data journalism to progress beyond being a passing fad, it must engage and include both readers and producers of news. Data journalism is not (only) about being smart and demonstrating your intelligence to the nation. There has to be more to it than that.

'Open Data' doesn't start with data. Rather, it starts with a question. Successfully applying data science to the practice of 'Open Data' requires more than providing context and finding clarity in the vast amount of unstructured data: it will sometimes require media organizations to think differently about how they work and who they venerate.

Understanding the impact of ODS in the context of Pakistan requires looking at the history of such systems. The initiation of such systems took place in the years back in 2010 that encouraged the country to initiate its formal open data system by developing various databases. Many challenges were experienced in the way to adopt open systems but were adopted keeping in view their ignorable advantages in managing the government affairs. Western countries took the lead in introducing such systems for better governmental performance. With the passage of time and based on the utility these systems provide, the eastern countries also started adopting these systems. This is because governments almost face similar problems in dealing with the general public and customer organizations that require authentic and timely information from the government departments. Their greater importance has compelled countries to prefer using such systems to stay clear about their functioning and responsibilities towards their citizens. This helps governments reduce corruption, and more clear and transparent information can easily flow towards the general public. Therefore, it is always recommended to use these systems to ensure that systems are crucial for a country's performance and enhance its social and political setup. Moreover, the GDP and economic growth can also be increased by avoiding wastage of resources like financial and other resources. Sharing government information is likely to result in the development of new governmental systems.

The use of open systems has importance for the residents' departments of the Government and general organizations operating under the Government's control to remain connected and share the information freely. This study remains significant by highlighting the value of open data for the economy of Pakistan. To achieve efficiency and effectiveness and get high targets, the country has to ensure better accountability and transparency in systems that are only possible by adopting and effectively using open data systems. Pakistan can fight corruption by integrating open data and participation in social and cultural development.

The lack of scholarly attention to fifth-generation warfare is most likely due to its limited validity. The phrase reminds me of another oft-repeated refrain: "hybrid war," a term coined by the transatlantic security community to describe Russian foreign policy and suspected acts of sabotage carried out by its intelligence. Critics argue that, like "fifth-generation war," "hybrid war" is a meaningless term that conflates disparate aspects of war with the practice of diplomacy.

Figure: 1 Controlling the Media in Iraq

DOI: <https://contexts.org/articles/controlling-the-media-in-iraq/>

Open Knowledge and Improved Transparency through Conflict Reporting

A transparent system can be developed by making information available in time and all the time. This should be the focal point to improve the Government's systems as the Britain government has done by connecting the taxpayers and collectors. This gives an edge to the Government to know about all the taxes collected, and there is no point of leakage of the tax money. The tax money is directly deposited into the Government's accounts that can be fruitfully used for development projects. This system ensures more transparency, and the society is thus called the open society where there are no boundaries of the sharing of information. This supports Government becomes accountable, and possible threats of corruption can be avoided well, as we see in the case of Europe. Ahonen-Rainio et al.'s (2014) report revealed various insights of the open data systems but has ignored the monetary effects in Euro terms. Another empirical examination by Koski (2011) shows that in fifteen nations, the introduction of geographic information was associated with fundamentally proved to be the faster means of development. In light of responses from 531 Finnish organizations, Koski's (2012) investigation found that in the Finish organizations, the era of new information-based administration has set in. The outcomes reaped are far more than the costs incurred, and administration improvements can be guaranteed in different organizations and areas. According to Kiuru et al. (2012), small firms can especially benefit rapidly from recently open information platforms introduced by the administration of various governments.

The Iraq War was a watershed moment in the history of war news. The embedded system's architecture and deployment allowed approximately 700 journalists to live and work alongside soldiers from the United States and United Kingdom armies. Nearly 30 countries participated in the system, including Spain, a major supporter of the USA's decision to initiate hostilities. This essay addresses the benefits and disadvantages of embedded systems and the threats they pose to journalists' security and privacy. It provides insight into the problems that will arise now that the embedded system has been consolidated as a means of resolving a dispute... and has often shown to be the most cost-effective method of doing so. This study reflects on the situation in Spain, where neither academics nor media have discussed this debate. The primary study instrument selected was an in-depth interview.

Evidence, misinformation, and "false news" are all tools of this ostensibly contemporary style of warfare. Following the publication of the EU DisinfoLab report, it was suggested that Pakistan is engaged in a different kind of holistic conflict, involving anything from bombs to bots. One issue with this claim is that the notion of "fifth-generation conflict" is not widely recognized by historians of foreign affairs or international security. The phrase "fifth-generation battle" does not occur in the material of five well respected peer-reviewed foreign relations or international security journals published in the last five years – International Security, Journal of Conflict Resolution, Journal of Peace Research, Journal of Strategic Studies, and Defense Studies – even though these journals have published approximately 5 million words. Strangely, such a new concept went unnoticed by business experts.

"Every war is a form of politics, but not every form of politics is a form of war."

Indeed, terms such as "fifth-generation battle" and "hybrid war" are often used to lend gravitas to a phony geopolitical review. Despite such extravagant arguments, by the early twentieth century, the practice of amplifying fissures in opponents' cultures was well established. Indeed, since the end of World War II, such tactics have been a standard component of counterintelligence operations. For example, during the Cold War, the Soviet Union and the United States also spread misinformation and deception. Under President Dwight Eisenhower, the US enthusiastically expanded the reach of its manipulation and psychological activities, eventually establishing an enormous system of organizations devoted to the cause, such as Voice of America and Radio Free Europe.

Figure: 2 Coverage of Civilian Casualties in Iraq

DOI:

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Coverage-of-Civilian-Casualties-in-Iraq/ff9573daec8dec421b05da459554a716ac58f785>

Embedded Journalism and Pakistan

Embedded Media is a term that applies to reporters assigned to military forces engaged in fighting conflicts. Though the word may be generalized to various past encounters involving journalists and military personnel, it first appeared in media reports of the 2003 Iraq invasion. The US military acted in response to criticism from the country's news media, who were dissatisfied with the amount of access provided during the 1991 Gulf War and the US invasion of Afghanistan in 2001. The tactic has been criticized as part of a recruitment scheme in which undercover journalists acted as cheerleaders and public relations agents for the occupying powers.

The USSR, for its part, relished the chance to report on American racism. Propaganda posters often juxtaposed icons of American independence, such as the Statue of Liberty, with symbols of segregation, racism, and domestic terrorism, such as the Ku Klux Klan or the police. The aim of this discussion is not to settle the concept of "fifth-generation battle." States run the risk of exaggerating the gravity of their adversaries' risks by treating disinformation and image control as war tactics rather than "natural" politics and diplomacy. While all war is political, not all politics is political, as famous Prussian military theorist Carl von Clausewitz noted.

This research offers a method for classifying conflict journalism in terms of its capacity for conflict escalation and de-escalation in Pakistan—a region rife with deadly conflicts. Using current research as a foundation, the analysis argues that the differing degrees of confrontation severity and the subsequent escalatory and de-escalatory coverage are critical factors in the process, via content review and focus group discussions determined that de-escalatory coverage is inversely proportional to a conflict's perceived vulnerability to national security. Second, it was discovered that coverage was distributed through various thematic backgrounds, though some views received greater exposure than others. Noting the differences in peace journalism, the study suggests that the vital pragmatic method is best adapted to addressing questions about its philosophy and experience than other alternatives since it accommodates the retention of peace as a value, thus being pragmatic and thereby meeting the requirements of the journalistic career.

The study analyzes the coverage of major conflicts in Pakistan by two prominent television networks, Geo TV and Dunya TV, to determine if the coverage is escalators or de-escalation. Its objective is to examine these tensions through the lens of peace journalism. The Taliban war, the Baluchistan conflict, ethnic conflict, and ethno political conflict in Karachi are among the wars. The thesis is essentially a comparative quality survey of media reports of disputes. The results imply that Pakistani news television channels focused on the Taliban and the ethno political crisis in Karachi in an escalating manner, ridden by a de-contextualized trend. On the other side, Baluchistan and sectarian violence are mostly recorded in de-escalations terminology due to various socio-cultural factors influencing coverage. The results are compatible with the current research on conflict journalism, which indicates that the media, in general, takes a more propagandist and nationalistic approach when threats to national security are perceived to be greatest while taking a more humanistic stance when threats to national security are perceived to be minimal. The only news that the media covered is drone attacks in the northern part of the country that bordered Afghanistan. Furthermore, due to lack of access to data, the reporters failed to recognize the real consequences of these attacks.

Figure: 3

DOI: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/428351/civilians-killed-from-us-drone-strikes-in-Pakistan/>

Open Data Impacting Lives of People

Worthy (2018) reported that open data systems impact the lives of people in three major ways that are;

1. Through the use of such systems, the Government stands more liable than ever before. It makes the Government well-organized, and the Government may become competent by extending effective public services (Stefaan& Andrew, n.a.).
2. These systems empower the residents by affecting the lives of citizens directly.
3. The governments can introduce advanced economic opportunities for the people living in the cities and/or remote areas for opening new industries and sectors.

Many governments have already provided an opportunity to their residents to access the data and information openly. Such as India has adopted open data, India has a governmental portal showing all the necessary information for the general public. At the same time, USA (data.gov.us) is an effective open data source benefiting its residents containing various types of relevant data. In Australia, the website (data.gov.au) provides accessible information to its public. Similarly, in New Zealand, (data.govt.nz) provide lists of various datasets extending help to people and in Pakistan the (data.gov.pk) is another useful platform.

Limitations and Future Direction

Embed opponents contended that the extent of military scrutiny was insufficient and that embedded journalists produced stories that were too favorable to the American side of the conflict, prompting the usage of the alternative word "imbedded journalist". "Those correspondents who ride about in tanks and armored personnel carriers," journalist Gay Talese said in an interview, "are spoon-fed by the military and become mascots for the military." If I had some influence, I would not have journalists embedded! ... Some things should be said that have not been told. That I have said several times."

What the 'Open Data' Obstacles are in related to fifth generation warfare in Pakistan? The main obstacle in Pakistan in using 'Open Data' understands what it is? There is also the non-serious attitude of Government when it comes to any positive use of technology. Today all the developed countries are using new digital tools to combat ills in their society. PAKISTAN still lacks behind as compared to other developing countries in term of using technology. There is no doubt that there are many sharp minds in Pakistan who are excelling in technology on individual level. Still, on government level there is no motivation and support for them. Nevertheless if only investigative journalists learn how to use 'Open Data' many positive changes can be made.

The open data systems influence the higher authorities, e.g. the Government, to ensure information transparency for social and political developments. Following alternatives can be used by the Government;

1. The public awareness about the latest technologies.
2. Sharing information for better engagement of the general public.
3. Upgrading ODS for the Government and public sectors.
4. A general framework for valuation should be developed so that the suggestions of people should be valued.
5. Conduct of scientific research for determining innovation

The primary goal of 5GW and hybrid warfare is to exploit domestic fault lines (political, economic, and societal). The incremental approach is meant to suffocate a state from within. The threat of 5GW and hybrid warfare is causing widespread concern around the world. The adversary targets the countries from inside, employing radicals and separatists as fronts in tens of thousands-strong cutback operation. Any conventional military adventure will be prohibitively costly for our enemies after the country's overt nuclearization. Our adversaries' preferred strategy has been to fight a nation in a hybrid war using nuclear weapons.

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